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Research Article

**INCIDENCE OF ASYMPTOMATIC SPONTANEOUS
BACTERIAL PERITONITIS IN PATIENTS WITH
DECOMPENSATED LIVER DISEASE AND ASCITES**Dr Komal Zainab¹, Dr Mala Ibrahim², Dr Mahnoor³¹Sharif Medical and Dental College, Lahore²Medical Officer at Islam Teaching Hospital, Sialkot³Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore

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Abstract:

Introduction: Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis is an ascitic fluid infection that occurs more frequently in patients with liver cirrhosis due to bacterial translocation and inadequate defense mechanisms to counter these bacteria. The most common symptoms may include abdominal pain, tenderness, fever, chills, but no symptoms.

Aim: The aim of the study is to determine the frequency of asymptomatic spontaneous bacterial peritonitis in patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis and ascites.

Place and Duration: In the medical Unit II of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Cases and methods: 140 cases were included in the study. After obtaining informed consent, an ascites fluid sample was taken and the presence of spontaneous bacterial peritonitis was analyzed by a complete biochemical and cytological examination.

Results: According to the age distribution of patients, 22 patients (15.7%) were 21-40 years old, 87 patients (62.15%) were 41-60 years old, 31 patients (22, 15%). He was aged 61-15. 70 years the mean age of patients was 53.27 ± 9 . Of the 140 patients, 73 (52.1%) were male and the remaining 67 (47.9%) were female. The incidence of asymptomatic spontaneous bacterial peritonitis was observed in 16 patients (11.4%).

Conclusion: Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis has been found in asymptomatic patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis.

Key words: translocation, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, ascites, decompensated liver cirrhosis.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cirrhosis is a serious and irreversible disease. It usually occurs as a result of hepatocellular damage and leads to fibrosis and nodular regeneration. Frequent complaints are caused by upper gastrointestinal bleeding, ascites, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, hepatic encephalopathy, and hepatocellular carcinoma and hepatorenal syndrome¹. Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis has previously been described as a sterile ascites fluid infection and there is no obvious source of infection in the abdomen. Patients with liver cirrhosis and ascites are more susceptible to spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP), the most common and life-threatening bacterial infection². More than 92% of SBP cases involve microorganisms (Gram-negative bacteria are responsible for two-thirds of all cases, and *Escherichia coli* is the most common, followed by *Klebsiella* species). It develops in 10-30% of hospitalized patients. Initially, when first described, mortality was > 90%. However, with early diagnosis of the disease and prompt and appropriate antibiotic treatment, hospital mortality due to PAN attacks decreased to around 20%³. Clinical manifestations of SBP are usually non-specific and include abdominal pain or tenderness, fever, chills, hepatic encephalopathy, and gastrointestinal motility disorders (vomiting, intestinal obstruction, diarrhea). One-third of patients with infected peritoneal fluid have no visible signs or symptoms, such as fever or abdominal pain, at the time of first admission⁴. Diagnosis is made on the basis of extensive studies of ascites fluid (cell number and culture susceptibility) after abdominal paracentesis⁵. A high total white blood cell count > 500 cells / mm³ or an absolute number of polymorphic nuclear cells (PMN) > 250 / mm³ or a positive culture is considered a diagnosis of SBP.

Patients with liver cirrhosis with spontaneous bacterial peritonitis may be asymptomatic, which means peritonitis such as abdominal pain, abdominal discomfort and fever, have no clinical symptoms⁶. Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis may be silent to diagnose SBP; Abdominal paracentesis is necessary to prevent complications such as septic shock, hepatorenal syndrome and hepatic encephalopathy⁷. There are several studies on asymptomatic SBP, but the results are different. An international study showed that the incidence of asymptomatic SBP was low, i.e. 3.5% and 5.4%,

local studies in Pakistan were quite high, i.e. 10% and 21%. The reason for this study is the lack of consistency in previous studies of the frequency of asymptomatic spontaneous bacterial peritonitis in Pakistan and abroad. Therefore, this study was conducted to determine the asymptomatic prevalence of PAS in the local population.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study is a cross-sectional study conducted in the medical Unit II of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. 140 patients with 95% confidence, 5% error margin and expected percentage of asymptomatic SBP were included.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients of any sex between 20 and 70 years old.
2. Patients with ascites-uncompensated liver cirrhosis (according to operational definitions).
3. Asymptomatic patients, i.e. no history of fever or abdominal pain.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patients who have taken antibiotics in the last two weeks.
2. Patients undergoing paracentesis for the last two weeks.
3. Patients with a history of upper gastrointestinal bleeding or bleeding in the past two weeks.
4. Patients who do not accept.

After obtaining informed consent, 10 ml of ascites sample of fluid was taken by paracentesis and the presence of SBP was confirmed.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed in SPSS 19. Age is a quantitative variable and mean and standard deviation calculated. The presence or absence of spontaneous bacterial peritonitis and gender were qualitative variables and data on this was calculated as frequency and percentage.

RESULTS:

During the six-month study period, 140 patients were enrolled in the period from 13/05/2014. To 11/12/2014. According to the patient age distribution, 22 patients (15.7%) were 21-40 years old, 87 patients (62, 1%) were between 41 and 60 years old, 31 patients (22.1%) were between 61 and 70 years old. The mean age of the patients was 52.14 ± 9.61 (Table 1).

Table 1: *Distribution of cases by Age.*

Age (Year)	Number	Percentage
21-40	22	15.7
41-60	87	62.15
61-70	31	22.15
Total	140	100
Mean $\pm$ SD	52.14 $\pm$ 9.61	

Graph 1: *Distribution of Cases by Age.***Table 2:** *Distribution of Cases by Sex.*

Sex	Number	Percentage
Male	73	52.1
Female	67	47.9
Total	140	100

Graph 2: *Distribution of Cases by Sex.*

Table 3: Frequency of Asymptomatic SBP.

Sample Positive for SBP	Number	Percentage
Yes	16	11.4
No	124	88.6
Total	140	100.0

Of the 140 patients, 73 (52.1%) were men and the remaining 67 (47.8%) were women (Table 2). PAS criteria were positive in 16 patients (11.4%) (Table 3).

DISCUSSION:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP) is a life-threatening complication of liver cirrhosis and the consequence of ascitic fluid infection⁸. Patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis in which ascites develops can become infected with this infection through bacterial translocation in the intestine. It develops in 10-30% of hospitalized patients. Mortality is high⁹⁻¹⁰. However, with early diagnosis of the disease and prompt and appropriate antibiotic therapy, mortality can be reduced after a PAS attack. SBP may have nonspecific symptoms such as abdominal pain or tenderness, fever, chills, hepatic encephalopathy and gastrointestinal motility disorders (vomiting, intestinal obstruction, diarrhea), but approximately one-third of patients with peritoneal fluid show no signs or symptoms. Like a fire, or stomach ache on first admission¹¹. Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis may be silent to diagnose PAS; Abdominal paracentesis is required even in asymptomatic patients to prevent complications such as septic shock, hepatorenal syndrome and hepatic encephalopathy¹². The incidence of asymptomatic SBP in patients with cirrhosis with ascites dissociation has been the subject of ongoing controversy. In our study, we found that the incidence of asymptomatic SBP was 11.6%¹³⁻¹⁴. Similar results were seen in a study conducted in the medical units of the Peshawar Khyber Training Hospital since July 2008. Until January 2009, this study showed that the incidence of asymptomatic SBP was 10%¹⁵. Another study conducted in India in 2011. H. pylori infection was found in 22 (63%) of 35 MHE patients.

CONCLUSION:

Data from our study showed that patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis were more likely to have asymptomatic spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP). Early diagnosis and treatment of SBP can prevent serious complications associated with SBP, such as septic shock, hepatorenal syndrome and hepatic encephalopathy.

Although PAS studies are not routine in patients with asymptomatic cirrhosis, it is important to consider this infection in all patients with asymptomatic cirrhosis to improve quality of life.

Further research is needed to assess SBP in patients with asymptomatic cirrhosis and to evaluate arguments against it.

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